

Viscosity of Liquids, their Boiling Points and Critical Temperatures.

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While working on the Andrade-Sheppard formula (*Nature*, 1930, 125, 309, 489) for the viscosity of liquids, $\log \eta = a + \frac{\beta}{T}$, where η represents viscosity, a and β constants, and T absolute temperature, a remarkable relation was found between β and the boiling point of the liquid expressed on absolute scale. In all the liquids examined the ratio of β to the boiling point of the liquid was found to be approximately constant, the ratio always lying between 1.04 and 1.24. Since the boiling points of liquids on the absolute scale are about 0.6 times the critical temperature expressed on the same scale, it was expected that a similar relationship would be found between β and critical temperature of liquids. In many cases the critical temperatures of the liquids are not known. In cases where the critical temperatures are known, it is found that the ratio of β to the critical temperature is a better constant, the ratio varying only from 0.64 to 0.73 as the following table shows.

Liquid.	β .	Boiling temp. T_B .	Critical temp. T_C .	β/T_B .	β/T_C .
Methyl iodide	330	315	528.5	1.05	0.64
Ethyl bromide	335	311	499.0	1.08	0.67
Ethyl iodide	358	345	554.0	1.04	0.65
Propyl chloride	362	319	494.0	1.10	0.73
Propyl bromide	380	344	—	1.10	—
Propyl iodide	409	375	—	1.09	—
isoPropyl chloride	372	310	—	1.20	—
isoPropyl bromide	390	333	—	1.17	—
isoPropyl iodide	411	362	—	1.13	—
isoButyl chloride	423	341	—	1.24	—

Liquid.	β .	Boiling temp. T_B .	Critical temp. T_C .	β/T_B .	β/T_C .
isoButyl bromide	440	364	—	1.20	—
isoButyl iodide	461	393	—	1.20	—
Allyl chloride	351	318	—	1.10	—
Allyl bromide	373	344	—	1.09	—
Allyl iodide	414	375	—	1.10	—
Chlorobenzene	468	405	635.2	1.15	0.73
Bromobenzene	488	429	670.0	1.14	0.73
n-Pentane	328	309	470.2	1.09	0.70
n-Hexane	370	341	523.3	1.08	0.71

Andrade has given a brief outline of his theory of the viscosity of liquids (*Nature*, 1931, 128, 835). Therein he considers the liquid state of matter to be more akin to the solid state. However, a relationship between β and the critical temperature means a relationship between β and Van der Waal's constants "a" and "b" for imperfect gases and unassociated liquids. From this it is apparent that β depends on the Van der Waal's constants. It is quite likely that if we use a formula like Van der Waal's equation instead of the simple gas law in the derivation of the viscosity of gases, we might get an equation involving "a" and "b" which might be true both for gaseous and liquid viscosities.

All the data for the viscosity of liquids were taken from Landolt-Börnstein's Tables. β for the various liquids was calculated from the above data.

SUMMARY.

(1) It has been shown that β/T_B and β/T_C are constants where T_B and T_C are the boiling points and critical temperatures of the liquids on the absolute scale, and β a constant occurring in the formula connecting viscosity and absolute temperature; $\log \mu = a + \beta/T$.

(2) Doubt has been expressed regarding the similarity in the liquid and solid state of matter suggested by Andrade.